

Practice 3. Genome assembly and comparative genome analysis.

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This protocol was adapted from: *David J. Edwards, Kathryn E. Holt. 2013. Beginner's guide to comparative bacterial genome analysis using next-generation sequence data. BMC Microbial Informatics*

1. Genome assembly and annotation

1.1 Downloading *E. coli* sequences for assembly

In this part of the tutorial, we will create a draft quality *E. coli* O14:H4 genome assembly to use in the comparative genome analysis. To start with we need sequences to assemble. For the worked example we are using Illumina HiSeq paired-end reads from *E. coli* O104:H4 strain TY-2482 (ENA accession SRR292770) –available here

<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/data/view/SRR292770&display=html>. Locate the 'Fastq files (ftp)' column and right-click on each of the two file links, choosing 'Save Link as...' to save them to your computer. These are in FASTQ format (see http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FASTQ_format) and compressed using gzip (you do not need to uncompress them).

Remember to download both forward and reverse reads (named 'SRR292770_1.fastq.gz' and 'SRR292770_2.fastq.gz'). Save these to a new folder (directory) with a suitable name, e.g. 'comparison'. This will be our working directory for the tutorial.

1.2 Examining quality of reads (FastQC)

Prior to attempting to assemble a set of reads, it is good practice to examine the reads to see if they are of good quality. A simple package to install and run to examine reads is FastQC.

Website: Download and install FastQC from

<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>.

The website also features examples of good and poor quality read sets for a number of sequencing platforms.

Compatibility: Java based, available for Windows, Linux and Mac OS X.

This tutorial was created using FastQC 0.10.1 on Mac OS X. Some versions of Java have been disabled on the Mac OS X, and if you do not have a version of Java higher than version 7u11 installed, you may need to follow the

suggestions in the FAQ for Java

(http://www.java.com/en/download/faq/java_mac.xml).

Inputs: forward and reverse read sequence files (FASTQ format) **Instructions**
Once FastQC has been installed, open the program to begin. Then:

1. To select the file sequence to check, use 'File > Open' in the FastQC menu. Navigate to the folder that you put the TY-2482 reads and select the 'SRR292770_1.fastq.gz' file. Make sure 'File Format' is set to 'Sequence Files', then hit the 'Open' button. FastQC will commence the analysis.

2. When the analysis has finished, you will be presented with a series of reports on the sequences. Select 'Per base sequence quality' to see a graph of the same. It should look like this:

You can also examine the other reports.

Note that this sequence set passes most of the tests, though the sequence duplication level is a little high (around 26%). The reads could be improved by removing duplicates by making use of a FASTQ quality control package such as the command line tools FASTX-Toolkit (http://hannonlab.cshl.edu/fastx_toolkit/)

or Trimmomatic (<http://www.usadellab.org/cms/index.php?page=trimmomatic>). However, as the reads for the tutorial are of otherwise good quality, we shall leave the important topic of quality control, and its pit-falls, for others to describe. The websites for the two packages are a good place to start, along with the supporting information for FastQC.

1.3 SPAdes – assembling reads into contigs

Website: Download and install SPAdes from <http://cab.spbu.ru/software/spades/>.

Instructional Reference: SPAdes manual <http://cab.spbu.ru/files/release3.10.1/manual.html>

Inputs: forward and reverse read sequence files (FASTQ format)

Instructions

The *de novo* assembly program SPAdes we used was installed ‘as is’ from the available binaries. Note that you will also need to add the SPAdes directory to your path, or use the full path to the ‘spades.py’ executable in the command below.

Basic command line usage of spades:

```
spades.py [options] -o <output_dir>
```

We need to run SPAdes in the same folder in which we storage the fastq files. Enter the following:

```
python spades.py -o spades_assembly -1 SRR292770_1.fastq.gz -2 SRR292770_2.fastq.gz --careful -t 2
```

-t: number of threads use at least 2

-o: options

--careful: Tries to reduce the number of mismatches and short indels. Also runs MismatchCorrector – a post processing tool, which uses [BWA](#) tool (comes with SPAdes). This option is recommended only for assembly of small genomes.

It will take just under 2 hours to complete the assembly using 3 threads; ~2 3/4 hours using the one. **So, we previously did the assembly that can be downloaded from the Moodle (SRR292770_unordered.fasta).**

3. Copy the contigs file from the SPAdes output folder and rename it :

```
cp spades_assembly/contigs.fasta SRR292770_unordered.fasta
```

You can then delete the output folder 'spades_assembly', though you may want to examine all the other outputs before doing so.

We have only used the default *k*-mer values (*k*-mer = 21, 33) rather than a set of 'optimal' values, these can be changed to examine how the choice of *k*-mers in SPAdes affects the contigs produced.

For those interested in assembling Ion Torrent sequence reads, we recommend you try MIRA (version 3, http://www.chevreux.org/projects_mira.html). This assembler is also useful for those interested in assembling reads from different sequencing technologies into the one assembly – MIRA is probably the best for this kind of assembly project. Once you have assembled the reads into contigs using MIRA, the rest of the analysis can make use of the tools and methods described here for Illumina-based reads.

1.4 Ordering contigs against a reference using Mauve

Once the sequence reads have been assembled into contigs, it is useful to order them against a suitable reference genome. One simple way to accomplish this is to use the 'Move Contigs' option available in *Mauve* (which is also used below for genome comparisons).

Website: <http://darlinglab.org/mauve/mauve.html> (Includes download links, installation instructions and user guide)

Inputs: These will be your newly assembled contigs and a reference genome – here we have chosen to use Ec55989 (NCBI accession NC_011748), a closely-related strain with a complete genome, available for download from NCBI. Go to moodle and download as NC_011748.fna.

If you don't want to run your own Spades assembly, you can do the rest of the exercises using pre-assembled *E. coli* O104:H4 contigs. Go to <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/wgs/?val=AFVS01&display=contigs&page=1> **[note: you will probably have to cut and paste this link directly into**

your browser] and click the 'Download' tab, then right-click the FASTA file to your computer and unzip it.

Instructions

Once you have installed Mauve and located your reference genome and contigs, we can order the contigs.

1. Launch the Mauve application.
2. From the Tools menu, select 'Move Contigs'.
3. A dialogue box should appear, with a box labelled 'Choose location to keep output files and folders'. Navigate to the folder with the sequences and the copied contigs, then click the 'Create New Folder' radio button. Give this folder a suitable name, e.g. 'MauveOutput' and then hit 'OK'.
4. A message should appear telling you about the iterative process involved in reordering the contigs. Take note of it, then hit 'OK' to dismiss it.
5. A dialogue box should appear, with a box labelled 'Align and Reorder Contigs'. Click the button below the box 'Add Sequence...' and navigate to the reference genome to align against, in this case 'NC_011748.fna'.
6. Click the 'Add Sequence...' button again and navigate to the FASTA file of the contigs you wish to align, 'SRR292770_unordered.fasta' from the assembly exercise above. Check that you have put the reference genome first, and the draft second, as expected by Mauve.

7. Click 'Start' to run the reordering. This might take half an hour or so total. A new window should appear marked 'Mauve Console' where the

progress of the run will be displayed, including any error messages (see below for an example). The reordering will take from four to seven iterations (for Mac OS X; even up to 16 iterations and a bit more time on a 32-bit Windows OS). A new window of the visualization tool should launch for each completed iteration, marked 'Mauve unknown – alignmentX', where X is the iteration number.

If you encounter errors, check that you have specified the right files for input – they should be FASTA or multi-FASTA sequence files.

8. Finally, a message telling you the reorder is completed should appear. Hit 'OK' and quit Mauve – though you can inspect the final alignment (and the others) beforehand.
9. The final set of ordered and oriented contigs are in the FASTA file located in the last of the iterated alignments. To find it, look in the 'MauveOutput' folder created above. For each iteration of the reordering there will be an output folder, so the final output is the contig file located in the subdirectory 'alignmentX' with the highest X, where X is the iteration number. Rename 'SRR292770_unordered.fasta' in this subdirectory, to 'SRR292770_ordered.fasta' and copy it to your main working directory (*i.e.* the one with the original sequence files, make sure you have changed the name of the ordered contigs file first as we will use the unordered contigs in a later exercise, *e.g.* 'SRR292770_unordered.fasta'. You can then delete the 'alignmentX' folders.

1.5 ACT – for concatenate contig sequences to a single-entry FASTA

Website: <http://www.sanger.ac.uk/science/tools/artemis-comparison-tool-act>
(To download, click the 'Downloads' tab) and look for the FTP download link for your operating system. Note that the download should contain Artemis as well as ACT.

Inputs: ACT can display pairwise comparisons between genomes. To do this it needs the genome sequences themselves (in FASTA format or annotated sequence format such as Genbank or EMBL files) and a comparison file. Comparison files can be created on your computer if you have BLAST installed, or using an online tool like WebACT (<http://www.webact.org/>) or DoubleACT (http://www.hpa-bioinfotools.org.uk/pise/double_actv2.html), see steps 1-2 below.

Instructions

Generating comparison files for ACT

1. Many application will not work with multi-FASTA sequences such as those containing several contig sequences as output by Sapdes or other assemblies. So, we first need to change the multi-FASTA contig sequences file into a FASTA file with a single entry, which includes all of our contig sequences concatenated together into one big sequence. An easy way to do this is to open the contig file in Artemis first.
2. Launch Artemis
3. Select File -> Open
4. Navigate to the location of your contig file in FASTA format and

click 'Open'. The contig sequences should be displayed, with the boundaries of each contig marked up as a feature and coloured in alternative orange/brown colours.

5. To write out the concatenated contig sequences to a single-entry FASTA file, select File -> Write -> All Bases -> FASTA Format and save name the new file something like 'SRR292770.fna' so you can easily identify this as a single-entry file.

1.6 Annotation using RAST

Website: <http://rast.nmpdr.org/> (need to register to use the service)

Inputs: Ordered contigs file (multi-FASTA format)

Instructions

In this example, we will generate a GenBank annotation for the newly assembled and ordered contigs of the *E. coli* O104:H4 strain in multi-FASTA format (use the contigs ordered against Ec55989, as we have done). **You must first register a for a RAST user account, though this is free of any charges.**

1. Go to <http://rast.nmpdr.org/> in a web browser and log into your account.
2. Under the 'Your Jobs' tab (top left corner) select 'Upload New Job'.
3. You should be taken to a page titled 'Upload your genome'. At the bottom of the page there is a box labelled 'File Upload:' click the button and navigate to your ordered contigs file ('SRR292770.fna'). Then hit the 'Use this data and go to step 2' button. This may take a little while as it is uploading your sequence file over your internet connection.
4. Eventually the next page will open with the same heading as the last, with the sub-heading 'Review genome data', and some contig statistics. You will be asked to enter further details about the organism. In the first field, labelled 'Taxonomy ID', enter the code for *E. coli* (562), and hit the 'Look up taxonomy ID at NCBI' button. This will populate the rest of the fields for you, except the last, the stain. Enter 'TY-2482' into the space for the strain, and then hit the 'Use this data and go to step 3' button.

(Note if you were doing this with something other than *E. coli*, you can find the right taxonomy ID at <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>).

- The next page should have sub-heading 'Complete Upload'. You can enter optional information (Sequencing Method = 'other', Coverage = '>8x', Number of contigs = "101-500"), but this is not necessary to use RAST. The other options for the RAST annotation pipeline should at least be considered, though we will use the default options as shown when the page first loads. Your final page should look like this:

Upload a Genome

Complete Upload

By answering the following questions you will help us improve our ability to track problems in processing your genome:

Optional information:

Sequencing Method Sanger Mix of Sanger and Pyrosequencing Pyrosequencing other

Coverage

Number of contigs

Average Read Length (leave blank if unknown)

Please consider the following options for the RAST annotation pipeline:

RAST Annotation Settings:

Select gene caller	<input type="text" value="RAST"/>	<i>Please select which type of gene calling you would like RAST to perform. Note that using GLIMMER-3 will disable automatic error fixing, frameshift correction and the backfilling of gaps.</i>
Select FIGfam version for this run	<input type="text" value="Release59"/>	<i>Choose the version of FIGfams to be used to process this genome.</i>
Automatically fix errors?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<i>The automatic annotation process may run into problems, such as gene candidates overlapping RNAs, or genes embedded inside other genes. To automatically resolve these problems (even if that requires deleting some gene candidates), please check this box.</i>
Fix frameshifts?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<i>If you wish for the pipeline to fix frameshifts, check this option. Otherwise frameshifts will not be corrected.</i>
Build metabolic model?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<i>If you wish RAST to build a metabolic model for this genome, check this option.</i>
Backfill gaps?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<i>If you wish for the pipeline to blast large gaps for missing genes, check this option.</i>
Turn on debug?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<i>If you wish debug statements to be printed for this job, check this box.</i>
Set verbose level	<input type="text" value="0"/>	<i>Set this to the verbosity level of choice for error messages.</i>
Disable replication	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<i>Even if this job is identical to a previous job, run it from scratch.</i>

If it does, hit the 'Finish the upload' to start the job. Your job will join the submission queue, and you will be sent an email (to the address you used

to register) when the job is completed. This could take a half a day or even much longer, depending on the number of jobs in the queue before you.

6. Once you receive the completion email from the Annotation Server, click on the link in the email to return to the RAST server (if you have logged out, you will have to log back in to continue). This time select 'Jobs Overview' under the 'Your Jobs' tab.
7. This will open the Jobs Overview page, where you will see a list of your jobs with a number of details and the status of the job. Click on the '[view details]' link for the job (in the 'Annotation Progress' column, under the green progress bars).
8. This opens the "Job Details" page and will include the available downloads if the job has completed. Select 'Genbank (EC numbers stripped)' and then hit 'Download'. The file will be called '562.<job_no.>.ec-stripped.gbk' – change this to 'SRR292770.gbk' and move the file to your work folder (where 'SRR292770.fasta' is located).

1.6.1 Alternatives to RAST

A number of command-line tools are available for annotation on a local machine. For fast *de novo* annotation we recommend trying Prokka (<http://www.vicbioinformatics.com/software/prokka.shtml>), though Prokka in turn relies on the installation of a long list of other programs (see the link for details). Also it uses a much-reduced database of proteins for annotation, so is not reliable for annotating protein functions in the way that RAST is.

For those interested in comparative annotation, you could try BG7 (<http://bg7.ohnosequences.com/>).

Otherwise, you now have an annotated draft genome for *E. coli* O104:H4 strain TY-2482, and can move on to the comparative genome analysis that follows.

2. Comparative genome analysis

2.1 Downloading *E. coli* genome sequences for comparative analysis

In this part of the tutorial, we will compare our *E. coli* O14:H4 genome assembly to other *E. coli* using various software packages on our computer. You will need to download the programs from the web using the links given in each section. In addition you will need to download some *E. coli* data for comparison.

For the Mauve and ACT comparisons, we will use these:

(This one we have already used above)

EAEC str. Ec55989 (NC_011748) – download NC_011748.fna from ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/archive/old_refseq/Bacteria/Escherichia_coli_55989_uid59383/

EHEC O157:H7 str. EDL933 (NC_002655) – download NC_002655.fna from

ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/archive/old_refseq/Bacteria/Escherichia_coli_O157_H7_EDL933_uid57831/

To compare the O104:H4 genome to enterohaemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) and enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC), we will also use these genomes:

- EPEC O26:H11 str. 11368 - NC_013361.gbk from

ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/archive/old_refseq/Bacteria/Escherichia_coli_O26_H11_11368_uid41021/

- EPEC O127:H6 str. E2348/69 - NC_011601.gbk from

ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/archive/old_refseq/Bacteria/Escherichia_coli_O127_H6_E2348_69_uid59343/

- aEPEC O111:H9 str. E110019 - AAJW02.gbk from

<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/wgs/?val=AAJW02> [**note: you will probably have to cut and paste this link directly into your browser**]

- EHEC O157:H7 str. TW14359 - NC_013008.gbk from

ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/archive/old_refseq/Bacteria/Escherichia_coli_O157_H7_TW14359_uid59235/

- EHEC O157:H7 str. EC4115 - NC_011353.gbk from

ftp://ftp.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genomes/archive/old_refseq/Bacteria/Escherichia_coli_O157_H7_EC4115_uid59091/

- EHEC O157:H7 str. Sakai - NC_002695.gbk from

ftp://ftp.ncbi.nih.gov/genomes/archive/old_refseq/Bacteria/Escherichia_coli_O157_H7_uid57781/

- Stx (shiga-toxin, or verotoxin) prophage VT2

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/5881592> *[note: you will probably have to cut and paste this link directly into your browser]*

- LEE pathogenicity island

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuccore/2897961> *[note: you will probably have to cut and paste this link directly into your browser]*

2.2 Mauve – for multiple genome alignment

We have already introduced Mauve above, for ordering contigs and inspecting assembly statistics.

In this example, we will generate a multiple alignment of the newly assembled and annotated O104:H4 outbreak genome (GenBank format) with an EHEC chromosome (NC_002655.fna) and the chromosome of EAEC strain Ec55989 (NC_011748.fba). We will then view the alignment and use it to inspect genes that are annotated in the outbreak genome but missing from the other pathogen chromosomes.

Inputs: Genome sequence files (FASTA format) and up to one annotated genome sequence (Genbank format).

Instructions

1. Launch the Mauve application
2. From the File menu, select 'Align with progressiveMauve...'
3. A dialogue box should appear, with a box labelled 'Sequences to align:'. Click the button below the box 'Add Sequence...' and navigate to your annotated genome (SRR292770.gbk, GenBank file generated by RAST).
4. Click the 'Add Sequence...' button again and navigate to the FASTA file of a genome you wish to align. In this case, we will start with the genome of the EHEC O157:H7 strain EDL933 (NC_002655.fna). If you provide a multi-FASTA file containing contigs, Mauve will concatenate these together before running the alignment.
5. Repeat step 4 to add any other sequences of interest. In our example we will just add the EAEC genome Ec55989.
6. Now we need to specify the output file. Click the button marked '...' to select an output file. Navigate to the directory in which you want the output to appear. Now specify a name for the output file (e.g. 'mauve_output') and click 'Save'.

7. Click 'Align...' to run the alignment. This might take half an hour or so. A new window should appear marked 'Mauve Console' where the progress of the run will be displayed, including any error messages.

If you encounter errors, check that you have specified the right files for input – they should all be FASTA or multi-FASTA sequence files, and can include up to one genome in Genbank format (to provide an annotation).

8. When the alignment is finished, the visualization tool will appear. To simplify the image a little, select View -> Style -> uncheck 'LCB connecting lines'. It should look like this:

Row 1 = annotated O104 genome.

Row 2 = EHEC genome

Row 3 = EAEC genome

Coloured blocks indicate regions of sequence with homology in the other genomes.

Red lines indicate contig boundaries.

You can save a static image of what you are viewing by selecting Tools -> Export -> Export image...

9. Notice the EHEC genome has more 'white space', *i.e.* sequences not in homology blocks, meaning these sequences are missing from the new O104:H4 genome and Ec55989. The other genomes have fewer white blocks, as they share a lot of their genome sequence.

To see what the 'unique' sequences are in the O104:H4 assembly, zoom in by clicking the '+' magnifying glass at the top of the window until you see boxes appear under the O104 sequence; these are annotated genes.

Scroll around to a region that is not within a coloured block, and mouse-over a gene to see its annotation. In our example, we are looking at a region of sequence in which IncI1 plasmid genes have been annotated. So, we know the O104:H4 genome assembly contains an IncI1 plasmid.